

Meadow Inventory Summary

May 30 – July 17 2025

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Invasive species

- Crown Vetch *Securigera varia*:
 - Dominant: Lower 1, Lower 4, Upper 1
 - Patchy: Lower 2, Lower 3, Lower 7, Lower 8, Lower 9, Lower 10, Middle 10, Middle 11, Middle 12, Middle 13, Upper 8, Upper 14, Upper 15, Upper 16
 - Rare: Lower 5, Lower 6, Middle 1, Middle 2, Middle 3, Middle 4, Middle 5, Middle 6, Upper 7, Upper 9, Upper 10, Upper 11, Upper 12, Upper 13
- Japanese Bramble *Rubus parrifolius*:
 - Dominant: Lower 2, Lower 4, Lower 5, Lower 7, Lower 9, Lower 10, Middle 1, Middle 8, Middle 9, Middle 10, Middle 11, Middle 12, Upper 1, Upper 2, Upper 3, Upper 4, Upper 5, Upper 6, Upper 8, Upper 9, Upper 11, Upper 13, Upper 14, Upper 15, Upper 16
 - Patchy: Lower 1, Lower 6, Lower 8, Middle 2, Middle 3, Middle 4, Middle 5, Middle 6, Middle 7, Middle 13, Upper 7, Upper 10
 - Rare: Lower 3, Upper 12
- Everlasting Pea *Lathyrus latifolius*:
 - Patchy: Lower 1, Lower 2, Lower 3, Middle 1
 - Rare: Lower 4, Middle 11, Middle 13
- Japanese Honeysuckle *Lonicera japonica*:
 - Patchy: Lower 1, Lower 3, Lower 4, Lower 7, Middle 10, Upper 9, Upper 15
 - Rare: Lower 2, Lower 5, Lower 6, Lower 8, Lower 9, Lower 10, Middle 1, Middle 4, Middle 5, Middle 6, Middle 7, Middle 12, Middle 13, Upper 1, Upper 4, Upper 5, Upper 8, Upper 10, Upper 14, Upper 16
- Oriental Bittersweet *Celastrus orbiculatus*:
 - Patchy: Lower 5, Lower 6, Lower 7, Lower 8, Lower 10, Middle 2, Middle 3, Middle 4, Middle 5, Middle 6, Middle 7, Middle 8, Middle 10, Middle 12, Upper 7, Upper 8, Upper 14, Upper 15, Upper 16
 - Rare: Lower 1, Lower 2, Lower 4, Lower 9, Middle 1, Middle 9, Upper 1, Upper 2, Upper 4, Upper 5, Upper 6, Upper 9, Upper 10, Upper 11, Upper 12, Upper 13
- Canada Thistle *Cirsium arvense*:
 - Patchy: Lower 3
 - Rare: Lower 1, Lower 2, Lower 5, Lower 7, Lower 8, Middle 12, Middle 13, Upper 12
- Duhurian Buckthorn *Rhamnus davurica*:
 - Patchy: Lower 2, Lower 4, Lower 9, Lower 10, Middle 10, Middle 11
 - Rare: Lower 3, Lower 7, Lower 8, Middle 2, Middle 8, Middle 9, Middle 12, Middle 13, Upper 1, Upper 3
- Autumn Olive *Elaeagnus umbellate*:
 - Patchy: Middle 10, Upper 14

- Rare: Lower 2, Lower 3, Lower 4, Lower 5, Lower 8, Lower 9, Lower 10, Middle 1, Middle 5, Middle 6, Middle 9, Middle 12, Middle 13, Upper 4, Upper 7, Upper 8, Upper 9, Upper 10, Upper 11, Upper 13, Upper 15, Upper 16
- Chinese Lespedeza *Lespedeza cuneata*:
 - Patchy: Middle 11
 - Rare: Upper 10
- Yellow Iris *Iris pseudacorus*:
 - Rare: Lower 1, Lower 3
- Johnson Grass *Sorghum halepense*:
 - Rare: Lower 1, Lower 2, Middle 1, Middle 3, Middle 6, Middle 7, Middle 8, Upper 10
- Japanese Stiltgrass *Microstegium vimineum*:
 - Rare: Lower 2, Middle 1, Middle 12, Upper 1, Upper 8
- Multiflora Rose *Rosa multiflora*:
 - Rare: Lower 3, Lower 4, Lower 5, Lower 6, Lower 9, Middle 12
- Wineberry *Rubus phoenicolasius*:
 - Rare: Lower 9
- Garlic Mustard *Alliaria petiolate*:
 - Rare: Middle 8
- Empress Tree *Paulownia tomentosa*:
 - Rare: Middle 10, Upper 9, Upper 14, Upper 15
- Joint-head Grass *Arthraxon hispidus*:
 - Rare: Middle 13
- Sheep Sorrel *Rumex acetosella*:
 - Rare: Upper 12

Rare / desired natives

- Narrow-leaved Sunflower *Helianthus angustifolius*: Lower 1
- New York Ironweed *Vernonia noveboracensis*: Lower 1, Lower 2, Lower 3, Lower 4, Lower 7, Lower 8, Middle 1, Middle 8, Middle 11, Middle 12, Dominant in Middle 13, Upper 2, Upper 4, Upper 6, Upper 7
- Golden Alexanders *Zizia aurea*: Lower 1
- Cup Plant *Silphium perfoliatum*: Lower 1, Upper 3
- Rattlesnake-master *Eryngium aquaticum*: Lower 3, Lower 6, Middle 2, Patchy in Middle 3, Middle 4, Middle 6, Middle 10, Middle 11, Patchy in Upper 3, Upper 11, Upper 13
- Green milkweed *Asclepias viridiflora*: Middle 6, Upper 16
- Smooth Blue Aster *Symphotrichum leave*: Middle 8
- Common Boneset *Eupatorium perfoliatum*: Middle 11, Middle 13
- Green Fringed Orchid *Platanthera lacera*: Middle 4, Middle 13
- Water Smartweed *Persicaria amphibia*: Middle 13
- False Boneset *Brickellia eupatorioides*: Middle 2, Upper 6, Upper 9, Upper 10, Upper 11, Upper 13
- Dense Blazing Star *Liatris spicata*: Upper 3

Seeded sections

Lower 1

This section has many oxeeyes (*Heliopsis*), yarrows (*Achillea*), and goldenrods (*Solidago*), which were all seeded. There is an abundance of natives in this plot compared to surrounding sections, especially Lower 2, which is heavily competing with Japanese bramble (*Rubus parvifolius*). However, the land in Lower 1 being disturbed for seeding has also led to a high abundance of nonnatives that thrive in disturbed soil, such as the spiny plumeless thistle (*Carduus acanthoides*) and the common mullein (*Verbascum thapsus*).

Lower 8

Goldenrod is documented as patchy in this section while Lower 9 has no goldenrod, which is also partially because Lower 9 is dominated by Japanese bramble. Goldenrod is also patchy in Lower 7, maybe because it was also seeded in that section or it has seeded itself over into the neighboring section. Joe-pyes (*Eutrochium*), yarrows, coreopsis, and New York ironweeds (*Vernonia noveboracensis*) are also found in Lower 8 after seeding, some of which are not found in Lower 7. However, they are rare in Lower 8. The disturbed soil also allows common mullein to become patchy in this section.

Middle 2

The prairie plots in this section have an abundance of young sprouts of the recently planted native wildflowers. While bedstraw (*Galium verum*), Japanese bramble, and big bluestem (*Andropogon gerardi*) are also found in these seeded plots, the several documented found species in each plot suggests that they can compete some with the section's dominant species.

Middle 8

Four species of goldenrod are found in this section, with early goldenrod (*Solidago juncea*) being a dominant species. The early goldenrod is also easy to spot as it is blooming during this time in July (Figure 1). Oxeyes and yarrows are also patchy in this section, along with the spiny plumeless thistle that thrived in the disturbed soil (Figure 2). Overall, many more forbes can be found in this section compared to surrounding sections, which is evident in that Middle 7 only has around 25 documented species, while Middle 8 has around 55.

Middle 13

This section has been dominated by the seeded tall goldenrod and New York ironweed. No other section in the meadow is this dominated by native forbes. Grass-leaved goldenrod (*Euthamia graminifolia*) and Joe-pye weed are patchy in this section as well. Japanese bramble and crown vetch (*Securigera varia*) are patchy, but them having to compete with the dominant forbes seems to be keeping them at bay, and allows for more species of forbes to be found and documented in this section. With this section being close to the wetland, species like the green fringed orchid (*Platanthera lacera*), water smartweed (*Persicaria amphibia*), and jewelweed (*Impatiens capensis*) are also found.

Upper 3

This small section is dominated by narrow-leaved mountain-mint (*Pycnanthemum tenuifolium*), Japanese bramble, and big bluestem. This section also has a diverse community of native species, including rattle-snake master (*Eryngium aquaticum*), yellow wild indigo (*Baptisia sphaerocarpa*), and dense blazing star (*Liatris spicata*) (Figure 3).

Upper 12

This section is dominated by yarrows, oxeyes, and switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*), which were all recently seeded. Nonnatives like bedstraw, green carpetweed (*Mollugo verticillata*), and nodding bristleglass (*Setaria faberi*) have become patchy in this section. Other sprouting native forbes may flourish in later seasons, which includes pale Indian plantain (*Arnoglossum atriplicifolium*), wild senna (*Senna hebecarpa*), and Canada milkvetch (*Astragalus canadensis*). Canada thistle (*Cirsium arvense*) is also found growing in this section, which might need management to prevent it from taking over.

Natural native communities

Middle 3

While bedstraw and big bluestem are dominant in this section, there is a significant patch of Pennsylvania blackberry (*Rubus pensilvanicus*), grass-leaved goldenrod, prairie rosinweed (*Silphium terebinthinaceum*), narrow-leaved mountain-mint, dogbane (*Apocynum*), and rattle-snake master. These plants are all decently deer-resistant, and have made a significant community within Middle 3. This section is difficult to move through with all of the thorny plants. It would be interesting to see if any non-deer-resistant forbes could be planted within this community, and would be safe within this deer-resistant patch (Figure 4).

Middle 8 and Middle 10

Communities of goldenrod paired with narrow-leaved mountain-mint and rattle-snake master are documented in these sections as well. Forbes that are deer-resistant seem to be successful (Figure 5).

Upper 4 and Upper 6

Black-eyed Susan (*Rudbeckia hirta*) is abundant in these sections, and is seen in communities with Pennsylvania blackberry, big bluestem, and narrow-leaved mountain-mint (Figures 6 and 7). The more deer-resistant plants could have helped protect the black-eyed Susans from deer when they were sprouts. The abundance of black-eyed Susans also suggests that these sections of the meadow are in a successional phase. It would be interesting to see if the black-eyed Susans fade out for longer lived perennials to take hold.

Upper 9 and Upper 10

Upper 9 has an abundant patch of narrow-leaved mountain-mint, as well as a large patch of smooth sumac (*Rhus glabra*) competing against the surrounding Japanese bramble (Figure 8). While most of the meadow is dominated by big bluestem grass, other native grasses like Indian grass (*Sorghastrum nutans*), little bluestem (*Schizachyrium scoparium*), and side-oats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) become more abundant in these sections. A small patch of Chinese lespedeza (*Lespedeza cuneata*) is also found in Upper 10, which might need to be treated before it spreads (Figure 9).

Upper 14

In these later Upper sections, Indian grass has become more dominant, and little bluestem becomes dominant in Upper 16. Upper 14 has three significant patches of species, which are winged sumac (*Rhus copallinum*), rose-pink (*Sabatia angularis*), and bigtooth aspen (*Populus grandidentata*) (Figures 10 and 11). The significant amount of rose-pink in the upper sections are likely due to the upper meadow burn from around a year and a half ago. Rose-pink is a biennial that thrives from seeding itself after burns, which is why they are abundant and in peak bloom in this upper section of the meadow.

Winged sumac and bigtooth aspen are only found in Upper 14, and are only found growing together as clonal species. The patch of bigtooth aspen is drawn around and marked in Avenza Maps. This will help confirm if the patch grows in later seasons. Autumn olive (*Elaeagnus umbellate*), which is rare in most upper sections, is more patchy in Upper 14 and might need to be treated.

Figure 1: Middle 8 Early Goldenrod *Solidago juncea* patch July 1 2025

Figure 2: Middle 8 Oxeye and Spiny Plumeless Thistle *Heliopsis helianthoides* and *Carduus acanthoides*
July 1 2025

Figure 3: Upper 3 Meadow Overview July 8 2025

Figure 4: Rattle-snake Master and Narrow-leaved Mountain-mint *Eryngium aquaticum* and *Pycnanthemum tenuifolium* patch Middle 3 June 17 2025

Figure 5: Middle 10 Overview June 30 2025

Figure 6: Upper 4 Meadow Overview July 8 2025

Figure 7: Upper 6 Meadow Black-eyed Susan *Rudbeckia hirta* patch July 9 2025

Figure 8: Upper 9 Meadow Smooth Sumac *Rhus glabra* patch July 15 2025

Figure 9: Upper 10 Meadow Chinese Lespedeza *Lespedeza cuneata* patch July 15 2025

Figure 10: Upper 14 Meadow Winged Sumac *Rhus copallinum* patch July 17 2025

Figure 11: Upper 14 Meadow Rose-pink *Sabatia angularis* patch July 15 2025